

Behaviour of Nitrophenols with *p*-Toluenesulphonyl Chloride. Part IV.

BY SHIAM SUNDAR JOSHI.

While studying the behaviour of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride with dinitrophenols in presence of diethylaniline (Sane and Joshi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 2481; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 299; 1932, **9**, 59), it was usually observed that when there were two nitro groups either in both the *ortho* positions, or the *ortho* and the *para* positions with respect to a hydroxyl group, the hydroxyl group was replaced by a chlorine atom. However, when there was a methyl group in the *meta* position with respect to the hydroxyl in the compounds previously studied namely, 3:5-dimethyl-2:4-dinitrophenol under similar experimental conditions no replacement took place, only esters were formed. This influence of a *meta* situated methyl group on the replaceability of a hydroxyl by a chlorine atom is not the same even in the case of similar dinitrophenols; thus in 3-methyl-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrophenol the hydroxyl group is replaced, as usual, by a chlorine atom but in 3-methyl-2-iodo-4:6-dinitrophenol no replacement could be effected, only an ester is obtained. Like the esters of other dinitrophenols, this ester is quite reactive and easily yields derivatives with ammonia and aniline.

It may here be noted that a similar influence of a *meta* situated methyl group was also observed while studying the additive compounds of dinitrohalogenobenzenes with pyridine. 3-Chloro-4:6-dinitrotoluene, 3-bromo-4:6-dinitrotoluene and 3-chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrotoluene did not yield additive compounds with pyridine, though other 2:4- and 2:6-dinitrohalogenobenzenes did so readily (Joshi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 313).

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Iodo-4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol was formed on treating a hot alcoholic solution of 4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol (2 g.) first with iodine (2.6 g.) and then with mercuric oxide in small amounts at a time; the cresol was obtained from it by filtering the hot liquid, removing the alcohol and extracting the residue with benzene. It is crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow crystals, m. p. 93°. (Found: N, 8.85. $C_7H_5O_5N_2I$ requires N, 8.64 per cent).

2-Iodo-4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate was obtained by heating together on a boiling water-bath for 4 hours 2-iodo-

4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol (3 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2 g.) and diethylamine (8 c.c.). The ester is slightly soluble in alcohol, more easily in acetone. It crystallises from a mixture of alcohol and acetone in colourless crystals, m.p. 136-37°, yield 4 g. (Found: S, 6.54. $C_{14}H_{11}O_7N_2IS$ requires S, 6.70 per cent).

The same ester was obtained by condensing the cresol with toluenesulphonyl chloride in presence of sodium carbonate solution.

2-Iodo-4:6-dinitro-m-toluidine results by passing dry ammonia through a solution of 2-iodo-4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresyl-*p*-toluene sulphate in an excess of alcohol for 45 minutes. It dissolves easily in the common organic solvents and crystallises from alcohol in yellow crystals, m. p. 97°, yield 2.8 g. (Found: N, 13.17. $C_7H_6O_4N_3I$ requires N, 13.0 per cent).

3-Methyl-2-iodo-4:6-dinitrodiphenylamine was obtained when 2-iodo-4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate (5 g.) and aniline (10 c.c.) were kept on a boiling water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. It crystallises from slightly diluted acetic acid in yellow crystals, m. p. 143-44°, yield 90%. (Found: N, 10.25. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4N_3I$ requires N, 10.53 per cent).

2-Bromo-4:6-dinitro-m-cresyl-p-toluenesulphonate was obtained by boiling in water 2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol (2.8 g.) and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2.1 g.) with small amounts of sodium carbonate (1.2 g.) at a time. The ester crystallises from acetone and alcohol in colourless crystals, m. p. 141°, yield 3 g. (Found: S, 7.19. $C_{14}H_{11}O_7N_2BrS$ requires S, 7.42 per cent).

2-Bromo-4:6-dinitro-m-toluidine was obtained by passing dry ammonia through a boiling alcoholic solution of 3-chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrotoluene (2.8 g.). It dissolves easily in common organic solvents. It crystallises from alcohol and also from dilute acetic acid in yellow crystals, m. p. 80°, yield 2 g. (Found: N, 15.02. $C_7H_6O_4N_3Br$ requires N, 15.22 per cent).

3-Methyl-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrodiphenylamine was obtained by boiling a solution of 3-chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrotoluene (1.5 g.) in alcohol, aniline (1 g.) and sodium acetate (1 g.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The compound dissolves easily in acetic acid and slightly in alcohol. It crystallises from alcohol in yellow crystals, m. p. 128°, yield 1.6 g. (Found: N, 11.81. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4N_3Br$ requires N, 11.93 per cent).